

Are advisors the primary providers of innovation support services in forestry and agriculture? Findings from LIAISON

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Susanne v. Münchhausen, Jekaterina Markow,
Anna Häring (HNEE), Evelien Cronien (ILVO),
Andrew Fieldsend (AKI),

**Eberswalde University
for Sustainable
Development**

ILVO

**Research Institute of
Agricultural Economics**

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Overview

1. Aim of the paper
2. LIAISON's field work
3. Conclusion

Particular emphasis on the role of farm advisory services

"Farm advisors can support collaboration for innovation better than others engaged in farm innovation."

"Yes, they speak farmers' language and at the same time, they understand the new solutions provided by science. They are the ones that bridge the gap between research and practice!"

Leading question for this paper

“In the past, classical farm advisory services were expected to spread the news about innovation in the farming community. But can they also steer and facilitate collaborative processes?”

What's an Innovation Support Service?

- Bring together the relevant actors (‘innovation brokerage’)
- Support the group’s application for funding
- Provide networking opportunities and enable knowledge exchanges
- Help to define the idea / clarify objectives (optional)
- Facilitate the co-innovation process (optional)
- Offer self-assessment exercises (optional)
- Mediate in case of a conflict (optional)

2. LIAISON's field work

Analysis for this paper is based on the review of 200 co-innovation partnerships from various sectors and geographical areas in Europe.

Results of the light-touch review

Our indicator: coordination of the studied projects.

- Researchers: 30.5% of the 200 from across Europe
- Farmers' organisations: 12%
- NGOs: 12%
- Public bodies: 11%
- Businesses: 7%
- Advisory organisations: 4%
(however, participating in more than half of the partnerships)

Reasons for becoming the coordinator

- Pre-existing relation to the project (‘natural nomination’)
- Expertise in proposal writing and coordination
- Available resources (time, money, staff)
- ➔ ‘Provision of ISS’ was not a reason (very few)

Match making and proposal writing

- Some cases: an organisation takes the lead and invites others or
 - Continuation of an earlier cooperation
 - Some others: public body set up the project
 - Large variety of constellations between organisations and their roles / responsibilities
- ➔ The type of organisation does not relate to the role in a co-innovation project.

Discussion: Arguments promoting farm advisory services to deliver ISS

PRO - Advisory services should be promoted to take the role of the ISS

They know the target group (farmers) that need information and innovative solutions

They are experts in **knowledge brokerage**

They have always been the facilitator between research and practice

Public advisory services can be instructed centrally - control of policy implementation

Advisors have to learn their soft skills anyway (listening, workshop facilitation etc.) and will profit from the additional training

CONTRA - Advisory services do NOT have to be promoted to become the ISS

Others such as scientists, producer organisations, businesses know the target group also very well

Others are experts in **innovation brokerage**

Advisors are technical specialists and needed as such. They are (too) expensive when working as facilitators (inefficient budget use)

Private services that provide support tend to be more efficient than public organisations

Facilitation of innovation processes requires special training and specific competences.

Conclusion

- Several types of actors may deliver similar services
(Not only classical farm advisors!)
- Instead, structures and context determine the best suitable candidate for the role of an ISS.
- Other factors than the type of organisation is decisive for the performance of an ISS.

Thank you!

liaison2020@hnee.de

[https://youtube.com/playlist?list=PLSwCCZQ
ECphqki10TZxJZmqNK6jj2fLI4](https://youtube.com/playlist?list=PLSwCCZQECphqki10TZxJZmqNK6jj2fLI4)

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At the @ifsa2022, Susanne @frvmuenchhausen and coauthors triggered a lively discussion with their conference paper “Are Advisors the Primary Providers of #Innovation #Support #Services in #Forestry and #Agriculture? The answer is No because the analysis indicates that the criteria ‘type of organisation’ is not decisive for the performance of an innovation support service. Instead, good cooperation in the past, functional capacities and resources available within any type of organisation as well as the sectoral, political and cultural context determine who is providing one or several functions of innovation support.

Excuse. These are some of the various services that define #innovation #support: bringing together the relevant actors (#innovationbrokerage); supporting the group’s application for funding; providing opportunities for #networking and #knowledge #exchange. Plus there are optional services such as helping to clarify the group’s objectives, the facilitation of the #coinnovation process, organisation of #selfassessment exercises or mediation in case of a conflict.

The underlying data stems from the 200 #interactiveinnovation partnerships that #LIAISON2020 teams studied from across Europe: Only 4% of the partnerships were led by an advisory service which were fewer than those led by scientists (30%) or by #farmers #organisations and NGOs (12% each). When it comes to the indicators ‘match making’ and ‘proposal writing’, again various constellations were found. For that reason, the authors could not support the hypotheses that #classical #farm #advisory services are in general more suitable than e.g. researchers, #rural #businesses, producer or any other #agrifood or forestry associations to grow into the role of innovation support service provision.

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